

How Do LLMs Encode Scientific Quality? An Empirical Study Using Monosemantic Features from Sparse Autoencoders

Michael McCoubrey^{1,*}, Angelo Salatino¹, Francesco Osborne^{1,2} and Enrico Motta¹

¹Knowledge Media Institute, The Open University, Walton Hall, Milton Keynes, MK7 6AA, United Kingdom

²Department of Business and Law, University of Milano Bicocca, Milan, IT

Abstract

In recent years, there has been a growing use of generative AI, and large language models (LLMs) in particular, to support both the assessment and generation of scientific work. Although some studies have shown that LLMs can, to a certain extent, evaluate research according to perceived quality, our understanding of the internal mechanisms that enable this capability remains limited. This paper presents the first study that investigates how LLMs encode the concept of scientific quality through relevant monosemantic features extracted using sparse autoencoders. We derive such features under different experimental settings and assess their ability to serve as predictors across three tasks related to research quality: predicting citation count, journal SJR, and journal h-index. The results indicate that LLMs encode features associated with multiple dimensions of scientific quality. In particular, we identify four recurring types of features that capture key aspects of how research quality is represented: 1) features reflecting research methodologies; 2) features related to publication type, with literature reviews typically exhibiting higher impact; 3) features associated with high-impact research fields and technologies; and 4) features corresponding to specific scientific jargons. These findings represent an important step toward understanding how LLMs encapsulate concepts related to research quality.

Keywords

Large Language Models (LLMs), Sparse Autoencoders (SAEs), Monosemantic Features, Research Quality Assessment, Research Impact Evaluation, Natural Language Processing (NLP)

1. Introduction

In recent years, the research evaluation community has increasingly investigated the potential of generative AI to support the assessment of scientific work [1, 2]. Several initiatives have emerged that employ large language models (LLMs) to evaluate, improve, or even generate research papers and other scholarly documents [3, 4, 5, 6]. These models have been applied, for example, to assist the peer review process for both papers [3] and grant proposals [7], and their adoption is expected to grow further. LLMs are also increasingly used to generate literature reviews [2, 8], demonstrating a strong ability to synthesise and summarise scientific knowledge, although the quality of current systems remains below optimal standards. Furthermore, recent studies have investigated how LLMs and related AI technologies can support the generation of novel research hypotheses [9, 10], as well as the synthesis of scientific knowledge into structured representations such as knowledge graphs [11, 12, 13] and scientific taxonomies [14, 15]. These advances suggest that such technologies may become integral components of the scientific discovery process. Beyond these research efforts, numerous studies have shown that LLMs are increasingly used in scientific writing, raising important ethical questions regarding authorship, bias, and transparency [1, 16]. These issues are becoming more pressing as the performance of LLMs continues to improve and their influence on research practice expands.

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*Corresponding author.

✉ michael.mccoubrey@open.ac.uk (M. McCoubrey); angelo.salatino@open.ac.uk (A. Salatino);

francesco.osborne@open.ac.uk (F. Osborne); enrico.motta@open.ac.uk (E. Motta)

🆔 0009-0002-8628-9417 (M. McCoubrey); 0000-0002-4763-3943 (A. Salatino); 0000-0001-6557-3131 (F. Osborne);

0000-0003-0015-1952 (E. Motta)

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Given the growing importance of LLMs as tools for scientific research and the production of scholarly materials, it is crucial to develop a deeper understanding of how they represent and encode concepts relevant to this domain, particularly the notion of scientific quality. While several studies [3, 7, 1] have shown that LLMs can, to some extent, evaluate research papers according to perceived quality, there remains a lack of research on the internal mechanisms that enable this capability. This gap is crucial, considering the central role of quality assessment in research evaluation.

Progress in this area has been limited partly because LLMs largely function as black boxes, whose internal reasoning processes are difficult to interpret. However, recent advances in LLM explainability have introduced promising approaches based on the concept of monosemantic features [17], which can offer new insights into how these models process and evaluate scientific information. Monosemantic features, typically identified using sparse autoencoders [18], are internal model representations that correspond to distinct and interpretable concepts, such as specific topics or entities.

This paper presents the first systematic investigation into how LLMs encode the concept of *scientific quality* through relevant monosemantic features. We address this question by identifying and analysing monosemantic features that are predictive of research quality across multiple models. The insights derived from this study represent an initial step toward explaining how the internal representations of LLMs capture this elusive yet fundamental notion, and how these features may contribute to a more transparent understanding of the ability of LLMs to assess and generate scientific research.

To identify the monosemantic features linked with research quality, we first extract such features using sparse autoencoders across three different configurations that employ Gemma 2 2B and Gemma 2 9B in combination with various autoencoders. The extracted features are then used to train a decision tree classifier that predicts the relative quality of research papers according to three bibliometric proxy indicators: 1) the citation count quartile of each paper, 2) the journal SJR quartile of the venue in which the paper was published, and 3) the journal h-index quartile of the same venue. The trained classifiers achieved fair performance across all tasks, indicating that the selected features are predictive of research quality, at least within the context of these proxies. We then analyse which specific features are most informative for each task and examine their presence across the three configurations. All experimental materials are available in the associated repository¹.

The results indicate that LLMs encode features associated with multiple dimensions of research quality. In particular, we identify four recurring types of features that emerge across dimensions and capture key aspects of how research quality is represented in textual form. These features suggest that LLMs internalise latent cues that humans also use, consciously or unconsciously, to assess the rigour, relevance, and impact of scientific work.

The first feature type relates to *research methodology*. LLMs appear to associate higher quality with texts that describe rigorous methodological approaches, whether qualitative or quantitative, and that explicitly mention the use of established research protocols or well-defined experimental procedures. The second type concerns the *publication type*. The models seem to recognise that survey papers and literature reviews tend to be of higher scholarly impact, possibly because they provide comprehensive overviews, methodological syntheses, or conceptual frameworks that guide subsequent research. The third type involves *research fields and technologies*. References to emerging, high-impact, or rapidly developing domains, subfields, or technologies appear to act as strong signals of perceived research importance. This suggests that LLMs capture topical trends and the social dynamics of research communities. Finally, we observe a less interpretable but intriguing group of features related to *academic language and specialised scientific jargon*. These patterns often correspond to community-specific terminologies and writing conventions, which may implicitly encode information about disciplinary identity and methodological preferences. A possible interpretation is that LLMs learn stylistic and lexical regularities characteristic of specific research communities. However, the precise role of this feature group remains unclear and warrants further investigation.

¹Repository - <https://github.com/McCoubreym/How-Do-LLMs-Encode-Scientific-Quality->

2. Related Work

In recent years, several initiatives have investigated the use of LLMs for evaluating scientific research and generating research-related content. These studies explore whether LLMs can emulate the analytical and evaluative capabilities of human experts.

A few studies have investigated the ability of language models to generate peer review scores and reports [3]. Although recent models can produce evaluations that are broadly comparable to those of human reviewers, challenges related to consistency, transparency, and bias remain unresolved. Related research has also explored the use of LLMs in grant peer review processes within funding organisations, such as the *la Caixa* Foundation [7]. Another emerging application is the automatic generation of related work sections using retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) pipelines [19], which are employed to produce summaries of the literature [2]. LLM-based systems have also been applied to reference recommendation [5, 4], the classification of research papers [20, 21, 22] and scientific sentences [23], hypothesis generation [9, 10], the construction of structured representations of scientific knowledge [12, 11], and the development of conversational agents for supporting literature analysis [6, 24]. These applications implicitly rely on the model’s capacity to identify rigorous and relevant research, suggesting that LLMs encode an internal notion of *research quality*. However, this capability remains poorly understood due to the opaque nature of current models.

To investigate how LLMs encode and reason about abstract concepts, recent research has introduced the notion of monosemantic features [17]. Unlike traditional embeddings that conflate multiple meanings, monosemantic features aim to disentangle distinct semantic dimensions into interpretable, context-independent components. They are typically identified using Sparse Autoencoders (SAEs) [18], which represent model activations through a sparse set of interpretable features. Recent studies have shown that this approach can uncover fine-grained, conceptually coherent structures often missed by conventional interpretability methods [25, 26].

In this paper, we extend the state of the art by being the first to investigate how LLMs represent the concept of research quality using the monosemantic feature methodology.

3. Methodology

In this section, we describe the methodology employed to identify monosemantic features that are predictive of high-quality research. The process comprised four main stages: 1) **data preprocessing**, which involved selecting and preparing the dataset; 2) **feature extraction**, performed by using LLMs and SAEs to generate research paper summaries and extract monosemantic features; 3) **model training**, which consisted of training decision tree classifiers on the extracted features across the three binary classification tasks; and 4) **qualitative analysis**, in which we examined the decision tree features to identify the monosemantic concepts associated with research quality.

The dataset used in this experiment was derived from the Academia/Industry DynAmics Knowledge Graph (AIDA KG) [27], a large-scale knowledge base comprising approximately 25 million Computer Science publications. The papers in this knowledge graph are described by a rich set of metadata, including authors, organisations, countries, venues, and associated research topics. For this study, we extracted a corpus of 38,639 papers and characterised each publication by its title, abstract, five-year citation count [28], and publishing journal. To provide additional context on journal quality, we enriched the dataset with two journal-level indicators: the SJR value and the h-index, both obtained from the Scimago Journal & Country Rank (SJR). The SJR value measures the scientific influence of a journal by considering both the number of citations it receives and the prestige of the citing journals [29]. The h-index reflects the journal’s productivity and citation impact, corresponding to the maximum number h such that the journal has published h articles that have each received at least h citations [30].

Although the publication metrics used in this analysis are imperfect proxies for research quality, they are utilised due to their widespread availability.

We then converted the three metrics of interest (citation count, SJR value, and h-index) into quartiles

Table 1

Accuracy of a decision tree classifier trained on monosemantic features extracted from different combinations of LLMs and SAEs across Tasks 1–3.

	LLM+SAE, 1 comb.	LLM+SAE, 2 comb.	LLM+SAE, 3 comb.	Task Avg	BERT Classifier
Task 1	0.6666	0.7211	0.6486	0.6788	0.6522
Task 2	0.7593	0.7463	0.7328	0.7461	0.8082
Task 3	0.7088	0.7351	0.7490	0.7310	0.8274
Avg. Model	0.7116	0.7342	0.7101	0.7186	0.7626

to capture relative performance levels across papers and journals. To focus on the most distinctive cases, we selected only the first (highest) and fourth (lowest) quartiles of each metric and constructed three balanced subsets for binary classification. These subsets are half the size of the full corpus of 38,639 papers. These subsets were designed to train classifiers for three specific prediction tasks regarding *Citation Count Quartiles*, *SJR Value Quartiles*, and *Journal h-index Quartiles*. Each dataset was split into training and test sets, following a 70:30 ratio.

Next, we extracted monosemantic features to serve as representations of the papers in the classification tasks. To this end, we explored different configurations to evaluate whether the extracted features remain consistent across various models and SAEs. Specifically, we employed the following settings: 1) Gemma 2 2B with the SAE *gemma-scope-2b-pt-res* (16k features version) at layer 20; 2) Gemma 2 9B-it with the SAE *gemma-scope-9b-it-res* (16k features version) at layer 20; and 3) Gemma 2 9B-it with the SAE *gemma-scope-9b-it-res* (16k features version) at layer 31 [31][32]. To extract the monosemantic features, we prompted each LLM to generate a three-sentence summary for every research paper. The prompts used for this task are provided in the repository. Subsequently, we computed the features for each token in the generated summaries using the SAE, and then averaged these features across all tokens within each summary. This procedure produced a single, interpretable vector for every research paper. A three-sentence summary was chosen to standardize the number of tokens being averaged, preventing length-based distortion in the paper-level features.

The resulting features were used as paper representations to train a decision tree classifier for the three binary classification tasks defined earlier. This classifier was selected because it 1) offers a highly interpretable representation of the decision-making process based on the input features, and 2) performs feature subset selection, ensuring that the resulting explanations depend on a limited set of features. The maximum number of leaf nodes was optimised for each task by evaluating model performance through cross-validation on the LLM & SAE combination 2. The optimised values for each task were then applied to the other settings to ensure comparability across decision trees. Finally, a standard BERT classifier [33] was trained to predict the quartiles of the research quality metric using a tokenised version of the same prompt adopted in the first setting. This experiment aimed to benchmark the performance of the decision trees against that of a state-of-the-art text classification model.

Following the generation of decision trees for each task, we performed a qualitative analysis to interpret the model’s predictive logic. To determine the conceptual meaning of each monosemantic feature in the resulting trees, we employed the Neuropedia service [34], which supports the investigation of feature behaviour by comparing texts with different activation values, identifying the tokens that maximally activate a feature, and observing how an LLM’s generated text changes when a feature’s activation value is artificially clamped to a fixed level. To further enhance the quality of the feature definitions, we examined the titles and abstracts of papers that displayed substantially different activation values for a given monosemantic feature of interest. After determining the meaning of individual features, our analysis aimed to group them into common themes to facilitate their interpretation.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, we first discuss the performance of the classifier and then analyse the most significant features for each task. Table 1 reports the classification accuracy of the classifiers across the three

Table 2

The monosemantic features for Task 1 (Predicting citation quartiles) across the 3 settings. Rows are ordered by setting number and feature importance. Blue index numbers indicate a positive association with the proxy metric, while orange ones indicate a negative association. More details about the decision trees are provided in Figures 1, 2, and 3 in the Appendix.

LLM & SAE	Index	Description
1	74	Overfocus on methodological details.
1	15676	Academic survey and reviews.
1	6631	Has an ambiguous definition. Likely linked to the length of the text.
1	2297	Names, particularly about technologies but can include people and institutions.
1	12691	Terms and phrases used in physics.
2	6135	Names of popular technologies e.g. big data, cloud computing, internet of things etc.
2	979	Academic survey and reviews.
2	15531	Has an ambiguous definition. Potentially about academic style of language.
2	13161	Tools related to inventions and innovations.
2	61	Has an ambiguous definition. Potentially about academic style of language.
3	12640	Names, particularly about technologies but can include people and institutions.
3	6355	Has an ambiguous definition. Potentially a methodology-focused paper.
3	2356	Academic survey and reviews.
3	6427	Has an ambiguous definition. Potentially related to the methods used.
3	3156	Names, particularly about technologies.

tasks. Because the dataset is perfectly balanced, accuracy was chosen as the evaluation metric. It offers the most intuitive measure of performance without the bias often found in imbalanced datasets, where F1-scores are typically required. It should be emphasised that the purpose of this study is not to achieve state-of-the-art classification performance. Instead, the classifiers are employed as analytical instruments to examine the information content and interpretability of the monosemantic features extracted from LLMs.

Interestingly, the decision tree classifier, which relies exclusively on the monosemantic features, performs slightly better than the BERT-based baseline in predicting the citation count quartile. This finding indicates that the monosemantic features capture meaningful and discriminative information relevant to this task. In contrast, the BERT classifier attains higher accuracy on the other two tasks, as expected for a model directly optimized on textual representations rather than interpretable features.

Considering the decision tree classifiers, the highest predictive performance was achieved for Task 2 (SJR quartile prediction), followed by Task 3 (journal h-index quartile prediction) and Task 1 (citation count quartile prediction). Overall, these results indicate that the monosemantic features extracted from the LLMs exhibit substantial predictive power with respect to the three metrics used as proxies for research quality.

The predictive performance remained broadly consistent across different combinations of LLMs and SAEs. The largest LLM (9B), when paired with an SAE at layer 20, achieved a slightly higher accuracy than the other configurations. This result suggests a modest benefit in using larger models and extracting monosemantic features from middle-layer activations.

The most influential features identified by the classifier varied across the three tasks. This variation indicates that the quality metrics capture distinct dimensions of research impact or possibly reflect different underlying phenomena. The citation quartile prediction task was distinctive, as the resulting decision tree structure was consistently reproduced across different LLM and SAE combinations. This finding suggests that the concepts underlying a paper’s citation count are more stable and coherent across models. In the following subsection, we provide a detailed discussion of the results obtained for the three tasks. Due to space constraints, we report only the main features, while the full classification trees are available in the appendix.

4.1. Task 1 - Predicting citation quartiles

The monosemantic features employed by the decision trees for task 1 are reported in Table 2. These features can be grouped into three main categories.

The first category concerns the **type of paper and the research methodology** (e.g., 979, 2356, 6355, 15676), that is, whether the publication is a survey, a literature review, or an empirical study. As expected, surveys and literature reviews tend to be associated with a higher citation count.

The second category concerns the presence of **specific technologies** (e.g., 2297, 13161, 3156, 12640). For instance, we identify features such as 6135 and 13161, which are directly associated with several popular technologies (big data, cloud computing, internet of things, Hadoop). This category is relatively easy to interpret, as publishing on emerging technologies at the right time often results in higher citation rates. Furthermore, previous studies have shown [35] that the use of such specific, topical keywords in the title and abstract is a key factor in Academic Search Engine Optimisation, which in turn improves the discoverability of a publication and can increase its citation count.

These first two categories of features indicate that the main themes emerging from the model are closely linked to a publication’s discoverability, which in turn shapes its citation impact. Discoverability depends on the publication’s nature and topical focus, as these influence how easily other researchers can locate and reuse its content. This interpretation accords with Information Foraging Theory [36], which views scientists as foragers seeking to maximise informational value while minimising search effort and uncertainty. Publications that bridge structural gaps or introduce reusable technologies strengthen the “information scent” of the literature, making them more visible and useful to others. As a result, they tend to attract citations rapidly, reflecting the interplay between information foraging and cumulative advantage in citation dynamics.

The third and more difficult category to interpret involves the use of **academic language** (e.g., 74, 61, 15531), which captures the extent to which a publication employs specialised scientific jargon. These may suggest that multiple subtle linguistic aspects may be linked with citation rates. However, the specific mechanisms behind this relationship are not yet clear. These features, therefore, warrant further investigation in future work.

4.2. Task 2 - Predicting SJR quartiles

The features that emerged as the best predictors for classifying papers according to the SJR quartile of their publication venue (reported in Table 3) differ substantially from those identified for predicting citation counts.

The first and most prominent group of features relates to **research fields and field-specific technologies**. These features typically indicate the disciplinary or technological focus of a publication and often reveal the subdomain in which the research is situated. Many of these field-related features were consistently retrieved across all three settings, confirming their strong relevance to this task. In particular, features associated with communication networks, electricity grids, data transmission, and business emerged as key indicators. The prevalence of these features suggests that certain domains are systematically associated with higher SJR quartiles. This can be partly explained by the structure of the SJR index [29], which, while normalising for subject area, still attributes greater weight to citations from more prestigious journals. As a result, papers in research areas where highly ranked journals frequently cite one another tend to be linked to venues with higher SJR values. This residual disciplinary bias creates a strong connection between the thematic content of a paper and the prestige level of its publishing journal.

A second important group of features concerns the **research methodologies** (e.g., 15378, 1715, 1063) adopted by the publications. These include explicit references to experimental protocols, such as randomised controlled trials, as well as methodological approaches based on machine learning and standard data processing techniques. Such features capture the analytical rigour and methodological design of the research rather than its topical focus. These features, which capture both the structural soundness and credibility of a study, appear to correlate with publication in higher-quality journals, suggesting that methodological rigor serves as a key indicator of perceived research quality. Their presence in the embeddings learned by the LLMs indicates an implicit understanding of the characteristics that define high-quality research.

Table 3

The monosemantic features for Task 2 (Predicting SJR quartiles) across the 3 settings. The order and colours follow the same convention as in the previous table. More details about the decision trees are provided in Figures 4, 5, and 6 in the Appendix.

LLM & SAE	Index	Description
1	7402	Reference to digital transmission codes.
1	16116	Refers to feature (particularly feature detection) used in machine learning.
1	8411	Has an ambiguous definition. References to mobile phones, wireless networks and sensors.
1	12691	Academic style language.
1	9954	Vehicle specifications.
1	4897	Has an ambiguous definition. Terms related to biological and physical activities.
1	12679	Has an ambiguous definition. The use of punctuation and formatting within sentences.
1	26	References to leadership, management, organisations.
1	15324	Standards for mobile communication e.g. GSM, LTE, LTE Advanced.
1	10026	Reference to computational complexity theory.
1	4785	Referring to a scientific research publication.
1	12938	Refers to electrical components and systems, particularly about the electric grid.
2	16326	Physics and engineering terms and concepts.
2	1582	Wireless communication technologies.
2	599	Computer vision.
2	14018	Terms related to ML feature extraction methods.
2	15358	References to academic publications and presenting academic work
2	4062	Words commonly within code and software development.
2	15378	Clinical trial and randomised controlled trials.
2	7671	Training CNN for computer vision and computer vision training features.
2	1063	Refers to correlations in data.
2	674	Has an ambiguous definition.
3	10403	Terms associated with data transmission particularly signal modulation.
3	12285	Image based machine learning e.g. denoising, reconstruction, decomposition, super-resolution.
3	9816	Standards for mobile communication e.g. GSM, LTE, LTE Advanced.
3	1715	Has an ambiguous definition. Related to algorithms and methods for data processing and analysis.
3	15246	Machine learning techniques.
3	15265	Words with the prefix 'it'. Mostly referring to information technology e.g. IT governance.
3	5001	Electricity grid technologies and management.
3	1436	Camera and image tasks, particularly camera calibration.
3	13675	Phrases related to copyright and licensing information.
3	15237	References to leadership, management, organisations.
3	15301	Statistical terminology.

4.3. Task 3 - Predicting journal h-index quartiles

The monosemantic features that emerged as strong predictors for classifying papers according to the h-index quartile of their publication venues (Table 4) combine elements identified in the previous two tasks. This overlap indicates that, although different metrics were used, they converge toward a shared latent dimension capturing a general notion of research quality or impact.

The first recurring theme, consistent with the previous analyses, involves **research fields and field-specific technologies** (e.g., software development, pedagogy). The relationship between these features and venue impact is somewhat weaker than in the earlier task, yet still evident. This indicates that the topical domain of a paper continues to affect the expected impact of its publication venue. Such an effect likely reflects both structural differences among disciplines in citation practices and temporary fluctuations in attention toward specific subfields.

A second prominent theme relates to the **research methodology** (e.g., 1392, 1618, 8721), which closely aligns with the analogous group of features identified in Task 1. These features capture whether a paper 1) adopts a literature review or survey-based approach, 2) employs a well-defined qualitative methodology, or 3) follows a quantitative approach grounded in standard data analysis techniques.

Their predictive power suggests that LLMs can internalise representations of research methodology and recognise textual cues associated with rigour and standardisation. Papers that adhere to established methodological norms tend to be associated with higher-quality venues, indicating that the model implicitly captures aspects of academic best practices.

Finally, as in the first task, we observe several features linked to **academic language** (e.g., 6278, 12691, 3864, 15358), encompassing specialized scientific terminology and stylistic conventions. One

Table 4

The monosemantic features for Task 3 (Predicting journal h-index quartiles) across the 3 settings. The order and colours follow the same convention as in the previous table. More details about the decision trees are provided in Figures 7, 8, and 9 in the Appendix.

LLM & SAE	Index	Description
1	9890	Educational methodology and technology.
1	6278	Acknowledging contributions and support from others in research.
1	1881	Software development language particularly about software architectures.
1	15324	Standards for mobile communication e.g. GSM, LTE, LTE Advanced.
1	12691	Complex academic language.
1	6465	Fuzzy logic/sets/values.
2	1392	Qualitative research methodologies.
2	1618	Data analysis techniques.
2	3864	Complex academic language.
2	5788	Technical terms and concepts related to telecommunications and networking.
2	3919	Contact information and author-related details.
2	15358	Common academic expressions.
3	8721	Discussion, exploring, or providing an overview/summary. Linked to literature reviews.
3	10557	Telecommunication technologies.
3	15809	Computing architectures and algorithms.
3	6980	Requests for or references to contact information.
3	2543	Pedagogic interventions.

plausible interpretation is that such linguistic markers signal disciplinary expertise and alignment with the norms of specific research communities, which in turn correlates with publication in more prestigious venues. This resonates with sociolinguistic observations that academic subfields often develop distinct linguistic and methodological identities. However, these linguistic features are the least interpretable, as their meaning can be subtle and context-dependent. Further investigation will be required to clarify how language use interacts with perceived research quality and venue impact.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents, to the best of our knowledge, the first systematic investigation into how LLMs encapsulate the concept of research quality. We extracted interpretable monosemantic features from LLM activations using sparse autoencoders and analysed their ability to act as predictors across three key scientometric tasks: predicting citation counts, journal SJR, and journal h-index. The results demonstrate that LLMs encode a rich and multidimensional representation of scientific quality, capturing information that aligns with established indicators of research excellence.

Our analysis revealed that the learned features reflect several conceptual dimensions of research quality, including 1) research methodologies, 2) publication type (e.g., survey), 3) high-impact research domains and technologies, and 4) specialised scientific jargon. These dimensions suggest that LLMs not only process linguistic information but also internalise patterns related to the epistemic and structural aspects of scientific communication. We discussed these findings in the broader context of research evaluation and made all experimental materials openly available to facilitate future studies.

This study presents some limitations that we aim to address in future work. First, the interpretation of monosemantic features inherently involves a qualitative component, as semantic labels are assigned by human researchers and may introduce subjectivity. Large-scale studies will therefore be essential to validate and refine these insights. Second, this work focused exclusively on Gemma 2 models, as they were particularly suited for the extraction of monosemantic features; extending the analysis to other architectures will help assess the generality of the results. Third, while this work classified publications into research quality quartiles, future studies could use regression to predict specific values. Finally, an intriguing direction for future research concerns how interpretable features can enhance LLM performance in tasks such as research evaluation, academic text generation, and hypothesis discovery, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of how artificial models capture the structure and quality of scientific knowledge.

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Appendix

Figures 1–9 present the decision tree models trained on the monosemantic features.

Figure 1: Decision tree obtained from Task 1 using the LLM & SAE combination 1. Feature definitions are provided in Table 2, where $activation_i$ denotes the feature with index i .

Figure 2: Decision tree obtained from Task 1 using the LLM & SAE combination 2. Feature definitions are provided in Table 2, where $activation_i$ denotes the feature with index i .

Figure 3: Decision tree obtained from Task 1 using the LLM & SAE combination 3. Feature definitions are provided in Table 2, where $activation_i$ denotes the feature with index i .

Figure 4: Decision tree obtained from Task 2 using the LLM & SAE combination 1. Feature definitions are provided in Table 3, where $activation_i$ denotes the feature with index i .

Figure 5: Decision tree obtained from Task 2 using the LLM & SAE combination 2. Feature definitions are provided in Table 3, where $activation_i$ denotes the feature with index i .

Figure 6: Decision tree obtained from Task 2 using the LLM & SAE combination 3. Feature definitions are provided in Table 3, where *activation_i* denotes the feature with index *i*.

Figure 7: Decision tree obtained from Task 3 using the LLM & SAE combination 1. Feature definitions are provided in Table 4, where *activation_i* denotes the feature with index *i*.

Figure 8: Decision tree obtained from Task 3 using the LLM & SAE combination 2. Feature definitions are provided in Table 4, where *activation_i* denotes the feature with index *i*.

Figure 9: Decision tree obtained from Task 3 using the LLM & SAE combination 3. Feature definitions are provided in Table 4, where *activation_i* denotes the feature with index *i*.